

14CNIT-1106

Endoreversible thermodynamic analysis of photothermal Vuilleumier refrigeration machines for sustainable cooling applications

Eduardo González-Mora^{1,*}, Ram Poudel², Ma. Dolores Durán-García¹

¹Universidad Autónoma del Estado de México, Cerro de Coatepec S/N, Toluca, México, Phone: +52-722-2140855 ext. 1240

²Appalachian State University, 397 Rivers Street, North Carolina, USA, Phone: +1-828-2626361

* egonzalezmo@uaemex.mx

1. Introduction

The current demand for cooling worldwide is substantial, accounting for approximately 19% of the total electricity used in buildings globally, or about 10% of all global electricity consumption [1]. The increased demand for cooling has several environmental impacts, including higher energy consumption, strain on power grids, and exacerbation of urban heat islands. To mitigate these impacts, it is essential to transition to low-carbon energy supplies, improve the efficiency of air conditioners, and integrate renewable energy resources in power production.

Nowadays, there are different technologies to produce cold. Some of them work through the use of renewable energy such as the sun. Solar cooling technologies can be divided into two categories: solar photovoltaic and solar thermal. Photovoltaic cooling systems, use solar panels to generate electricity, which is then used to power a cooling system. Solar thermal cooling systems, on the other hand, use solar energy to generate heat, which is then used to drive a cooling process [2].

Solar thermal cooling technologies encompass a diverse range of approaches [1,2]. The most prevalent among these is vapor compression, a widely adopted refrigeration system that utilizes a circulating liquid refrigerant to absorb and expel heat from the designated area. As an alternative to vapor compression, absorption-based cooling incorporates absorption and adsorption chilling, leveraging adsorbents to address associated drawbacks. Evaporative cooling, another method in this spectrum, employs water evaporation to cool the air, offering a cost-effective and energy-efficient solution, particularly effective in dry climates. Solar ejector cooling, relying on ejectors, employs pressure changes for the vaporization and evaporation of liquid, efficiently cooling components and their surroundings. This versatile cooling technique has found practical application in both air conditioning and refrigeration, underscoring its adaptability and relevance in diverse contexts within the field.

However, an alternative that has not been explored extensively is the Vuilleumier systems. Vuilleumier cooling machines, also known as Vuilleumier refrigerators, are a unique type of heat-driven cooling device that operates according to the Vuilleumier cycle [3]. In this paper, we explore for the first time the use of concentrated solar thermal energy to drive a Vuilleumier.

2. Materials and methods

A Vuilleumier cycle is a special cycle used for low-temperature cooling applications [4]. In essence, a Vuilleumier cycle is a special combination of a heat engine and a cooling machine through four reversible isothermal and four reversible isochoric processes (refer to Fig. 1) [5,6]. The sequence of the cycle is:

Engine segment:

- 1 to 2: \dot{Q}_H enters at T_H (isothermic expansion)
- 2 to 3: Isochoric heat release (regenerator charged)
- 3 to 4: $\dot{Q}_{out,1}$ released at T_W (isothermic compression)
- 4 to 1: Isochoric heat addition (regenerator discharged)

Refrigerator segment:

- 1' to 2': Isochoric heat release (regenerator charged)
- 2' to 3': \dot{Q}_L enters at T_L (isothermic expansion)
- 3' to 4': Isochoric heat addition (regenerator discharged)
- 4' to 1': $\dot{Q}_{out,2}$ released at T_W (isothermic compression)

Where the total heat release is $\dot{Q}_{out} = \dot{Q}_{out,1} + \dot{Q}_{out,2}$. When the regenerator is not ideal ($\varepsilon < 1$), and using the ratio $r_e = \frac{V_3}{V_4} = \frac{V_2}{V_1}$, we can define the heat exchanger factor $\zeta = \frac{(1-\varepsilon)c_v}{R \ln r_e}$ ($\zeta = 1$ in the ideal case), where R is the gas constant and c_v , the specific heat at constant volume of the gas, it is easy to demonstrate that the coefficient of performance (β) is:

$$\beta_{max} = \frac{\frac{T_L}{T_W - T_L} - \zeta}{\frac{T_H}{T_H - T_W} + \zeta} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Ideal Vuilleumier cycle.

Table 1 shows some characteristics parameters of Vuilleumier coolers reported in the open literature. The T_H temperatures are within the range that can be easily obtained with concentrating solar systems. Hence, it is of interest to explore the performance limit that could be reached with this configuration, by extending the generalized model of converting solar radiation into work [7].

Table 1. Inextensive typical parameters of Vuilleumier refrigerators. Adapted from [4].

Case	T_L , (K)	T_W , (K)	T_H , (K)	β_{max}
1	263	313	773	3.130
2	285	313	873	6.529
3	285	318	973	5.814
4	273	323	773	3.179
5	262	306	853	3.818
6	273	318	693	3.283

2.1 General model for a solar Vuilleumier refrigerator

Now, consider the modified schematic in Fig. 2, and its respective $T - s$ diagram. The engine segment receives radiation from the Sun (T_H), using an optic (solar concentrator) to supply heat to the Vuilleumier cycle (where the absorber is coupled to the heat engine segment at T_a). In parallel, the cooling segment absorbs heat from a cold enclosure (T_L). The model is developed under the following assumptions:

- The Vuilleumier machine is not necessarily a reversible device
- The system goes under steady-state operation
- The absorber is considered as a Lambertian black body
- The temperatures are homogeneous at the interfaces
- The energy and entropy fluxes are computed by $\varphi = \xi \sigma T^4$ and $\psi = \frac{4}{3} \xi \sigma T^3$

The concentration-acceptance product $\xi = C_g f$, where C_g is the concentration ratio of the solar concentrator and f is the view factor between the sun and the absorber.

Fig. 2. Solar Vuilleumier cycle.

3. Results and discussion

For the engine segment, the energy balance in the absorber and the engine:

2

$$A_a(\varphi_H - \varphi_a) = \dot{Q}_a \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{W} = \dot{Q}_a + \dot{Q}_{reg,e} - \dot{Q}_{out,1} \quad (3)$$

where $\dot{Q}_{reg,e} = Fmc_v(1 - \varepsilon)(T_a - T_W) = \gamma(1 - \varepsilon)(T_a - T_W)$ is the regenerator heat exchange, considering a constant F rpms, with $\gamma = Fmc_v$ as a displacement parameter that characterizes the Vuilleumier cycle. The entropy balance in the engine segment:

$$\frac{\dot{Q}_a}{T_a} + \dot{S}_{gen}^e + \gamma \ln \left(1 + \frac{2T_a}{T_W} \right) - \frac{\dot{Q}_{out,1}}{T_W} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Now, for the refrigerator segment, the energy and entropy balance:

$$\dot{W} = \dot{Q}_r + \dot{Q}_{reg,r} - \dot{Q}_{out,2} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\dot{Q}_L}{T_L} + \dot{S}_{gen}^r + \gamma \ln \left(1 + \frac{2T_W}{T_L} \right) - \frac{\dot{Q}_{out,2}}{T_W} = 0 \quad (6)$$

For a Vuilleumier refrigerator, the coefficient of performance is defined by:

$$\beta = \frac{\dot{Q}_L}{\dot{Q}_H} \quad (7)$$

Putting equations 2-7 together, we have in the general case:

$$\beta = \frac{T_L}{T_W - T_L} \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{1}{\xi} \left(\frac{T_a}{T_H} \right)^4 \right) \left(1 - \frac{T_W}{T_a} \right) + \frac{\gamma}{A_a \sigma \xi T_H^4} \left[(1 - \varepsilon)(T_a - 2T_W - T_L) - T_W \ln \left(\frac{T_L T_W - 2T_a}{T_W T_L - 2T_W} \right) \right] - \frac{T_W \dot{S}_{gen}^{tot}}{A_a \sigma \xi T_H^4} \right\} \quad (8)$$

For a reversible cycle ($\dot{S}_{gen}^{tot} = \dot{S}_{gen}^e + \dot{S}_{gen}^r = 0$), Eq. (8) reduces to:

$$\beta_{max} = \frac{T_L}{T_W - T_L} \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{1}{\xi} \left(\frac{T_a}{T_H} \right)^4 \right) \left(1 - \frac{T_W}{T_a} \right) + \frac{\gamma}{A_a \sigma \xi T_H^4} \left[(1 - \varepsilon)(T_a - 2T_W - T_L) - T_W \ln \left(\frac{T_L T_W - 2T_a}{T_W T_L - 2T_W} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (9)$$

To estimate the maximum β of the Vuilleumier refrigerator the following condition must be met: $\frac{d\beta}{dT_a} = 0$, and can be demonstrated that the resulting equation is a sixth-degree polynomial equation that has no analytical solution:

$$8T_a^6 - 10T_a^5 T_W + 3T_a^4 T_W^2 - \frac{2\gamma}{A_a \sigma} T_a^3 (1 - \varepsilon) + \frac{\gamma}{A_a \sigma} T_a^2 T_W (3 - \varepsilon) - 2T_a T_H^4 T_W \xi + T_H^4 T_W^2 \xi = 0 \quad (10)$$

Solving Eq. 10 numerically for T_a allows defining the optimal temperature that maximizes the coefficient of performance (β). It is important to note from both Eq. 9 and 10, in addition to β depending on the surface temperatures as well as the concentration geometry, depends also on the physical configuration of the absorber (A_a) and the displacement factor γ of the Vuilleumier machine.

For example, consider a Vuilleumier radiative refrigerator with different concentrators geometries. We will set the absorber area to 1 m², using 1 kg of air ($c_v = 0.717$ kJ/kg·K) as the working fluid and an operating frequency of 1100 rpm. Having the Sun as the heat source, $T_H = 5777$ K, and assuming the environment is at standard conditions, $T_W = 298.15$ K, and from Table 1, we will set $T_L = 273$ K. Thus, it is possible to determine the coefficient of performance β as a function of concentration geometries ξ .

Fig. 3. Coefficient of performance for the solar Vuilleumier refrigerator.

Fig. 3 presents the functional dependence of β on ξ computed using numerical solution of Eq. 9 and 10. As shown the coefficient of performance is 0 when $\xi < 0.13$, so not all the concentration geometries can be used to achieve the cooling effect of the Vuilleumier machine. Nevertheless, for high collection optics ($\xi \rightarrow 1$), the coefficient of performance (β) reaches logarithmic asymptotic behaviour close to 8 for the chosen operating conditions.

4. Conclusions

This study explores an integration of concentrated solar energy with Vuilleumier refrigeration machines, leveraging an endoreversible thermodynamic framework to evaluate their performance and sustainability under different concentration geometries. By deriving generalized analytical expressions for the Coefficient of Performance (β), we have established critical relationships between operating conditions, absorber characteristics, and concentration geometry. These results offer a theoretical foundation for optimizing the design and operation of solar-powered Vuilleumier machines.

This research presents an endoreversible thermodynamic model for the Vuilleumier radiative refrigerator, marking a significant advancement in understanding the coupling of solar concentrators with such machines. May be first of its kind, our analysis demonstrates that the coefficient of performance increases logarithmically with higher optical concentration geometries, achieving a maximum under specific configurations. This finding underscores the importance of high-efficiency concentrators and customized absorber designs in enhancing system performance. Furthermore, the study confirms that the temperature ranges achievable through solar concentration align well with the operational requirements of Vuilleumier refrigeration cycles, emphasizing their compatibility and feasibility for practical applications.

The implications of this work extend beyond the theoretical study, presenting a viable pathway for integrating renewable solar energy into sustainable cooling technologies. These machines offer potential complementary solutions to mitigate the environmental and energy challenges associated with traditional refrigeration methods, particularly in regions with abundant solar resources.

This study has some limitations, including assumptions of steady-state operation and ideal absorber behavior. Future research should focus on dynamic analyses, alternative working fluids, and advanced materials to address these constraints and to further enhance system performance. A field-scale implementations and hybrid configurations will also be essential to improve the technology readiness level of this integrated system for a wider application.

5. References

- [1] IEA, *The Future of Cooling*, Paris, 2018.
- [2] S. Karellas, et al., *Solar cooling technologies*, 1st ed., CRC Press, 2018.
- [3] J. Wurm, et al., *Stirling and Vuilleumier Heat Pumps: Design and Applications*, 1st ed., McGraw-Hill, 1991.
- [4] T. Guo, et al., Analytical model for Vuilleumier cycle, *International Journal of Refrigeration* 113 (2020) 126–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrefrig.2020.01.026>.
- [5] G. Dogkas, et al., A review on Vuilleumier machines, *Thermal Science and Engineering Progress* 8 (2018) 340–354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsep.2018.09.004>.
- [6] R. Paul, et al., Cooling Cycle Optimization for a Vuilleumier Refrigerator, *Entropy* 23 (2021) 1562. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e23121562>.
- [7] E. González-Mora, et al., A practical upper-bound efficiency model for solar power plants, *Journal of Non-Equilibrium Thermodynamics* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1515/jnet-2022-0080>.